

1 **New insights on homogenization for hexagonal-shaped**
2 **composites as Cosserat continua**

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7 **Abstract** In this work, particle composite materials with different kind of mi-
8 crostructures are analyzed. Such materials are described as made of rigid particles
9 and elastic interfaces. Rigid particles of arbitrary hexagonal shape are considered
10 and their geometry is described by a limited set of parameters. Three different
11 textures are analyzed and a static analysis is done to show a comparison among a
12 discrete, a micropolar (Cosserat) and a classical model. In particular, the displace-
13 ments of the discrete models are compared to the displacement fields of equivalent
14 micropolar and classical continua realized through a homogenization technique,
15 starting from the representative elementary volume (RVE) detected with a nu-
16 meric approach. The performed analyses show the effectiveness of adopting the
17 micropolar continuum theory for describing such materials.

18 **Keywords** Composite materials · Cosserat theory · Homogenization · RVE ·
19 Hexagonal shaped particles · Finite Element Method

20 **1 Introduction**

21 Composite materials can be investigated by directly describing their constituents
22 in a micromechanical discrete model or by homogenizing them as equivalent con-
23 tinua. In the former case, for example to study heterogeneous materials such as
24 polycrystalline materials, jointed rock systems, and block masonry with periodic
25 microstructures [1] [2], the model involves a system with a large numbers degrees
26 of freedom and as a consequence the computational costs is very high [3]; such
27 cost increases by reducing the material scale [4] [5]. In the latter case, by using ho-
28 mogenization techniques, the numerical analyses are faster and more efficient but
29 it is fundamental to define equivalent continua that properly takes into account

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30 the influence of the microstructure on the macro-scale behavior [6] [7] [8] [9] with
31 particular reference to shape, size and texture of elements [10]. When classical
32 kinematics is enriched with extra degrees of freedom for instance, homogenization
33 procedures have been shown to provide more reliable models than in the case of
34 classical local continua [11] [12] [13] [14].

35 The selection of macroscopic continuum theories, which retain memory of the
36 fine internal structure of the material is a fundamental point. Among various ho-
37 mogenization techniques, the development of methods and conceptual guidelines
38 for continuous field descriptions by linking discrete and continuum solid mechan-
39 ics is a topic of crucial importance in materials science [15] [16] [17]. Many non-
40 classical and non-local continuous models, such as micropolar models (Cosserat),
41 show the advantages of a coarse-scale field description while keeping the mem-
42 ory of the fine organization of the material and in particular of material internal
43 length. A model can be defined as non-local due to the presence of both internal
44 length scales and dispersion properties, revealing in some cases the existence of
45 an underlying microstructure which inevitably affects the macroscopic mechanical
46 properties [18] [19]. In such non-local models the governing equations contain one
47 or more parameters that take in account material internal lengths and present
48 dispersion properties in wave propagation [13] [14] [20] [21] [22] [23].

49 Within these models, micromorphic continua, in particular continua with rigid
50 local structures (micropolar) which present additional degrees of freedom, can be
51 classified as 'implicit/weak' non-local models [24] [25] [26]. The literature shows
52 that they have been satisfactorily applied to various composites [12] [27] [28] [29]
53 [30] [31] [32] [33] [34]. Different works moreover, [35] [36] [37] [38] [39] [40] [41], pro-
54 posed multiscale computational homogenization with 'explicit' non-local or higher
55 order deformation gradient theories in composite materials [42] [43] [44] [45] [46].
56 In particular non-local models with gradient elasticity has been used to study
57 one-dimensional structures such as beams and rods [47] [48].

58 In this work, a micromechanical approach based on the scale dependent discrete-
59 continuum homogenization procedure defined in [31] [32] [33] for particle composite
60 materials, addressed to derive the macroscopic mechanical properties of a micropo-
61 lar continuum, is adopted. The micropolar theory, beside the standard displace-
62 ment, introduces the rotation of the material point, termed microrotation, to be
63 distinguished with the macrorotation (local rigid rotation). When the relative ro-
64 tation, i.e. the difference between micro and macrorotation, is null the micropolar
65 continuum, under some other dynamical constraints, behaves as a couple stress con-
66 tinuum [12]. As the effects of the relative rotation are expected to be prominent
67 for strongly anisotropic particle composites, as widely investigated in [11] [49] [50]
68 for masonry-like materials, we consider here the full (unconstrained) micropolar
69 theory.

70 In order to highlight the advantages of micropolar elasticity description, the
71 numerical solutions of equivalent micropolar and classical continua, obtained by
72 putting some internal constraint to the micropolar model [49], are compared to the
73 one of a discrete model assumed as benchmark solution. The discrete numerical so-
74 lution has been obtained using the ABAQUS software in which the single blocks are
75 rigid and elasticity is concentrated at the interfaces through elastic linear springs
76 (joints) while for the continuum, classical and micropolar, solution, an in-house
77 FEM code has been performed [51] [52]. Moreover, an investigation is proposed in
78 order to detect the representative volume element for hexagonal shaped compos-

ites. This geometry is typical for some polycrystals with thin interfaces such as Alumina (Al_2O_3), Zirconia (ZrO_2), Zinc Oxide (ZnO) or Tungsten-Carbide (WC). Considering a generic tile (e.g., orientation of the interfaces and internal angles of the hexagonal geometry) different material symmetries can be detected [53]. The hexagonal shaped composites are investigated starting from the previous works [51] [54] and in particular considering three microstructure geometries [55].

In this paper, at first Cosserat theoretical aspects are briefly presented (Sec. 2) and then the geometries of microstructured composites are introduced, in particular by studying the unit cell to detect the RVE necessary for the homogenization procedure (Sec. 3). Later the numerical implementation of the continuum model is shown (Sec. 4), the discrete model assumed as benchmark solution is properly described and finally a static analyses comparison among the discrete system, the micropolar and the classical continuum for a 2D panel is reported (Sec. 5).

2 Cosserat theoretical framework

The Cosserat model can be considered equivalent to an assembly of rigid particles undergoing homogeneous displacements and rotations which interact with each other via forces and couples. Therefore, it is suitable for simulating the mechanical response of granular, masonry-like and composite materials with either periodic or random microstructure [30] [31] [34].

For the present study a 2D rectangular panel with three different hexagonal microstructures is considered. In a linearized 2D framework there are two displacements and one rotation component, so that the generalized displacements $\underline{u}^T = [u_1 \ u_2 \ \omega]$ applies. The strain displacement vector is $\underline{\varepsilon}^T = [\varepsilon_{11} \ \varepsilon_{22} \ \varepsilon_{12} \ \varepsilon_{21} \ k_1 \ k_2]$, where $\varepsilon_{11}, \varepsilon_{22}, \varepsilon_{12}, \varepsilon_{21}$ are the in-plane normal and shear strains and k_1, k_2 are the micropolar curvatures. Note that the strain components are not symmetric $\varepsilon_{12} \neq \varepsilon_{21}$. Moreover, the microrotation ω is different from the local rigid rotation (microrotation) θ , defined as the skew-symmetric part of the gradient of displacement $\theta = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial u_2}{\partial x_1} - \frac{\partial u_1}{\partial x_2} \right)$ and the difference between the two rotations $\theta - \omega$ defines the strain measure of the relative rotation, corresponding to the skew-symmetric part of the strain. When the relative rotation equals zero $\theta = \omega$ then $\varepsilon_{12} = \varepsilon_{21} = \frac{\partial u_2}{\partial x_1} - \frac{\partial u_1}{\partial x_2}$ as in the classical continuum, the micropolar continuum becomes a continuum with constrained rotations, that under other dynamical constraints, is a couple stress continuum [12] [56].

The stress vector is represented as: $\underline{\sigma}^T = [\sigma_{11} \ \sigma_{22} \ \sigma_{12} \ \sigma_{21} \ \mu_1 \ \mu_2]$ where σ_{ij} for $i, j = 1, 2$ represent the classical normal and shear stress components and μ_1, μ_2 are the microcouples. The stress components are not reciprocal, $\sigma_{12} \neq \sigma_{21}$ and the couple stress components μ_1, μ_2 have to be introduced in order to satisfy the moment equilibrium of the micropolar body.

The kinematic compatibility relations can be written as:

$$\underline{\varepsilon} = \underline{D} \underline{u} \quad (1)$$

119 where:

$$D = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_1} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{\partial}{\partial x_2} & 0 \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial x_2} & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & \frac{\partial}{\partial x_1} & -1 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{\partial}{\partial x_1} \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{\partial}{\partial x_2} \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

120 From the virtual work principle, equilibrium equations in terms of stresses and
121 microcouples can be carried out as $\delta U + \delta V = 0$, being δU the internal work:

$$\delta U = \int_V \delta \underline{\underline{\varepsilon}}^T \underline{\underline{\sigma}} dV = h \int_A \delta \underline{\underline{u}}^T (\underline{\underline{D}}^T \underline{\underline{\sigma}}) dA \quad (3)$$

122 and δV the potential of external loads, that in 2D domain takes the form:

$$\delta V = - \int_V \delta \underline{\underline{u}}^T \underline{\underline{f}} dA - \int_S \delta \underline{\underline{u}}^T \underline{\underline{p}} dS \quad (4)$$

123 where $\underline{\underline{f}}$ and $\underline{\underline{p}}$ are the vectors of body forces and boundary tractions, respectively.

124 Balance domain equations are then given by:

$$\underline{\underline{D}}^T \underline{\underline{\sigma}} = \underline{\underline{f}} \quad (5)$$

125 and boundary tractions as:

$$\underline{\underline{p}} = \hat{\underline{\underline{p}}} \quad (6)$$

126 where $\hat{\underline{\underline{p}}}$ are respectively, contact forces and couples applied at the boundary.

127 The micropolar anisotropic constitutive equations take the form:

$$\underline{\underline{\sigma}} = \underline{\underline{C}} \underline{\underline{\varepsilon}} \quad (7)$$

128 where:

$$\underline{\underline{C}} = \begin{bmatrix} A_{1111} & A_{1122} & A_{1112} & A_{1121} & B_{111} & B_{112} \\ & A_{2222} & A_{2212} & A_{2221} & B_{221} & B_{222} \\ & & A_{1212} & A_{1221} & B_{121} & B_{122} \\ & & & A_{2121} & B_{211} & B_{212} \\ & & & & D_{11} & D_{12} \\ sym & & & & & D_{22} \end{bmatrix} \quad (8)$$

129 Due to hyperelasticity, the constitutive matrix is symmetric ($\underline{\underline{C}} \in Sym$).

130 Accounting for the constitutive equations, the internal work can be write:

$$\delta U = \int_V \delta \underline{\underline{\varepsilon}}^T \underline{\underline{\sigma}} = \int_V \delta \underline{\underline{\varepsilon}}^T \underline{\underline{C}} \underline{\underline{\varepsilon}} dV = h \int_A (\delta \underline{\underline{u}}^T \underline{\underline{D}}^T \underline{\underline{C}} \underline{\underline{D}} \underline{\underline{u}}) dA \quad (9)$$

131 In Sec. 4 the principle of virtual work will be adopted for the numerical imple-
132 mentation.

133 **3 Microstructure geometry**

134 The geometry of the microstructure is realized considering a six edges parallel-
 135 ogram and it is possible to give different input settings to set the shape: the
 136 main parameters are the angles α_1 , α_2 and α_3 and the relative length (Fig. 1),
 137 $l_r = 100/(1/\sqrt{3} + 1)$ that defines the ratio between $AB \equiv DE$ and $BD \equiv AE$, l_1 ,
 138 l_2 , l_4 , l_5 are defined as: $l_2 = s \cdot l_r \cdot 0.01$ where s is the microstructure scale factor,
 139 $l_1 = 1 - l_2$; $l_4 = 0.5 \tan(\alpha_2)$; $l_5 = 0.5 \tan(\alpha_3)$.

Fig. 1: Hexagonal shape pattern and single tile for the parameters: $\alpha_1 = 25^\circ$, $\alpha_2 = 45^\circ$, $\alpha_3 = 30^\circ$ and $l_r = 40$.

140 Keeping constant the lengths, and varying the angles α_2 and α_3 it is possible to
 141 obtain different geometries; in particular for $\alpha_2 = 0$ and $\alpha_3 = 0$ the lateral edges
 142 of hexagonal shape are vertical therefore the parallelogram acquires a rectangular
 143 shape. In this paper, for the patterns studied, the angles α_2 and α_3 assume the
 144 values: $\alpha_1 = \alpha_2 = 30^\circ$ for the regular hexagonal shape, $\alpha_1 = \alpha_2 = -20^\circ$ for the
 145 hourglass shape and $\alpha_1 = -\alpha_2 = -30^\circ$ for the skew shape. Finally, by varying
 146 the relative scale the three geometries reported in Fig. 2 are obtained by setting
 147 the scale factor s : where $s = 1$ for large blocks, $s = 0.5$ for medium blocks and
 148 $s = 0.25$ for small blocks. The ratios among the parameter l_2 of microstructure
 149 shape and the vertical side L_y of panel analyzed in Sec. 5 are: $l_2/L_y = 0.0411$,
 150 $l_2/L_y = 0.0823$ $l_2/L_y = 0.0205$.

Fig. 2: Microstructure textures at different scales $s = 1, 0.5, 0.25$: a)-c) Regular Hexagon d)-f) Hourglass g)-i) Skew.

151 3.1 Representative Volume Element

152 The homogenization procedure adopted for deriving the material constants of the
 153 micropolar continuum is the one defined in [31] [32], where at the fine level the
 154 material is described as a system of rigid blocks, here named elements, interacting
 155 through elastic contact elements, here referred as joints, the interaction is repre-
 156 sented by forces and couples. A kinematical correspondence map between discrete
 157 and continuum fields is assumed (generalization of the Cauchy-Born rule) and an
 158 energy equivalence criterion is adopted. To apply the homogenization procedure
 159 for periodic assemblies it is necessary to firstly define the Representative Volume
 160 Element (RVE), as the elementary volume element (unit cell) made of the minimal
 161 number of elements and joints sufficient to completely define the behavior of the

162 discontinuous and heterogeneous material. As the micropolar continuum is intrin-
 163 sically scale-dependent, the definition of the RVE requires particular attention.

164 For the following analyses it is convenient to represent the constitutive matrix
 165 (8) in the form:

$$\underline{C} = \begin{bmatrix} \underline{A} & \underline{B} \\ \underline{B}^T & \underline{D} \end{bmatrix} \quad (10)$$

166 It is possible to show that only the constitutive components of \underline{B} and \underline{D} contain
 167 internal length scales, and this also justify the classification as 'implicitly' non local
 168 material [26].

169 In order to define the RVE, here by exploiting the results of numerical simu-
 170 lations performed comparing micropolar and discrete solutions (Sec. 3.1.2), with
 171 the latter solution assumed as benchmark, two different unit cells are considered.

172 3.1.1 7-Blocks unit cell

173 In the first case, the unit cell is constituted of one central block and six joints, there-
 174 fore seven elements are considered. The common edges interact by the medium
 175 point of the joint and the calculations of material constants are referred to the
 176 gravity center of the cell.

Fig. 3: Seven blocks unit cells: a) Regular Hexagon b) Hourglass c) Skew.

177 The constitutive matrix for regular hexagonal shape is:

$$\underline{A}_{reg} = \begin{bmatrix} 1189.7 & 170.0 & 0 & 0 \\ 170.0 & 1189.7 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 849.8 & 170.0 \\ 0 & 0 & 170.0 & 849.8 \end{bmatrix}; \underline{B}_{reg} = [0];$$

$$\underline{D}_{reg}^{(s=1)} = \begin{bmatrix} 39.8 & 0 \\ 0 & 28.5 \end{bmatrix}; \underline{D}_{reg}^{(s=0.5)} = \begin{bmatrix} 10.0 & 0 \\ 0 & 7.1 \end{bmatrix}; \underline{D}_{reg}^{(s=0.25)} = \begin{bmatrix} 2.5 & 0 \\ 0 & 1.8 \end{bmatrix}$$

178 It is worth noting that for the regular hexagons the constitutive matrix coeffi-
 179 cients are such that $A_{1111} = A_{2222}$, $A_{1212} = A_{2121}$; there is no coupling between
 180 normal stresses and shear strains (tangential strains and longitudinal strains), mi-
 181 crocouples $D_{12} = 0$ as well as $\underline{B}_{reg} = \underline{0}$. This configuration, invariant with respect
 182 to $\frac{\pi}{4}$ rotations, belongs to the orthotetragonal material symmetry class [31]. A

183 small Poisson effect is shown. Furthermore, it is possible to observe that the com-
 184 ponents of \underline{A} do not change with the decrease of scale, while the terms \underline{B} and \underline{D}
 185 depend on s ; in particular, approximately, $\underline{D}_{reg}^{s=1} \approx 4 \underline{D}_{reg}^{s=0.5} \approx 16 \underline{D}_{reg}^{s=0.25}$.

186 The constitutive matrix for hourglass shape is:

$$\underline{A}_{hour} = \begin{bmatrix} 584.4 & -126.1 & 0 & 0 \\ -126.1 & 2539.9 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1927.4 & -126.1 \\ 0 & 0 & -126.1 & 346.7 \end{bmatrix}; \underline{B}_{hour} = [0];$$

$$\underline{D}_{hour}^{(s=1)} = \begin{bmatrix} 16.6 & 0 \\ 0 & 59.8 \end{bmatrix}; \underline{D}_{hour}^{(s=0.5)} = \begin{bmatrix} 4.2 & 0 \\ 0 & 15.0 \end{bmatrix}; \underline{D}_{hour}^{(s=0.25)} = \begin{bmatrix} 1.0 & 0 \\ 0 & 3.7 \end{bmatrix}$$

187 For the hourglass shape, the scale effect is always shown by the terms \underline{D} ; in
 188 particular $\underline{D}_{hour}^{s=1} \approx 4 \underline{D}_{hour}^{s=0.5} \approx 16 \underline{D}_{hour}^{s=0.25}$. The negative terms $A_{1122} = A_{2211}$
 189 show the auxetic behavior of the microstructure.

190 Finally, the constitutive matrix for skew shape is:

191

$$\underline{A}_{skew} = \begin{bmatrix} 793.1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1784.6 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1274.7 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 566.5 \end{bmatrix},$$

$$\underline{B}_{skew}^{T(s=1)} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 124.4 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}; \underline{B}_{skew}^{T(s=0.5)} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 62.2 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}; \underline{B}_{skew}^{T(s=0.25)} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 31.1 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\underline{D}_{skew}^{(s=1)} = \begin{bmatrix} 26.6 & 0 \\ 0 & 42.7 \end{bmatrix}; \underline{D}_{skew}^{(s=0.5)} = \begin{bmatrix} 6.6 & 0 \\ 0 & 10.7 \end{bmatrix}; \underline{D}_{skew}^{(s=0.25)} = \begin{bmatrix} 1.7 & 0 \\ 0 & 2.7 \end{bmatrix}$$

192 In this case there is no Poisson effect, $A_{1122} = A_{2211} = 0$, and differently
 193 from the previous cases there is a coupling between elastic coefficients relating
 194 stresses and curvatures ($\underline{B} \neq 0$), in particular there is coupling between normal
 195 stress σ_{22} and curvature k_2 . For this microstructure matrices \underline{B} and \underline{D} shows
 196 scale dependence, and in particular approximately $\underline{B}_{skew}^{s=1} \approx 2 \underline{B}_{skew}^{s=0.5} \approx 4 \underline{B}_{skew}^{s=0.25}$,
 197 $\underline{D}_{skew}^{s=1} \approx 4 \underline{D}_{skew}^{s=0.5} \approx 16 \underline{D}_{skew}^{s=0.25}$.

198 3.1.2 4-Blocks unit cell

199 In this case the unit cell considered is constituted of a system of four blocks with
 200 five joints, centered at the central joint.

Fig. 4: Four blocks unit cells: a) Regular Hexagon b) Hourglass c) Skew.

201 The constitutive matrices are different from the cases above. The new matrices
202 are:

203 For the regular hexagons:

$$\underline{A}_{reg} = \begin{bmatrix} 1189.7 & 170.0 & 0 & 0 \\ 170.0 & 736.5 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 623.2 & 170.0 \\ 0 & 0 & 170.0 & 849.8 \end{bmatrix}; \underline{B}_{reg} = [\underline{0}];$$

$$\underline{D}_{reg}^{(s=1)} = \begin{bmatrix} 39.8 & 0 \\ 0 & 20.9 \end{bmatrix}; \underline{D}_{reg}^{(s=0.5)} = \begin{bmatrix} 10.0 & 0 \\ 0 & 5.2 \end{bmatrix}; \underline{D}_{reg}^{(s=0.25)} = \begin{bmatrix} 2.5 & 0 \\ 0 & 1.3 \end{bmatrix}$$

204 It can be useful to observe that the constitutive matrices for the regular
205 hexagon shapes are not orthotetragonal, the terms $A_{1111} \neq A_{2222}$, $A_{1212} \neq A_{2121}$
206 as in the 7-blocks regular hexagon case because the joints are not in a symmetric
207 configuration, invariant with respect to $\frac{\pi}{4}$, therefore in this case the symmetry is
208 lost homogenizing from the discrete system to the continuous system in an equiv-
209 alent energetic approach [31]. The micropolar term \underline{D} is scale dependent with the
210 same ratio as in the above case, approximately $\underline{D}_{reg}^{s=1} \approx 4 \underline{D}_{reg}^{s=0.5} \approx 16 \underline{D}_{reg}^{s=0.25}$.

211 The constitutive matrix for the hourglass shape is:

$$\underline{A}_{hour}^{(s=1)} = \begin{bmatrix} 584.4 & -126.1 & 0 & 0 \\ -126.1 & 1547.2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1431.1 & -126.1 \\ 0 & 0 & -126.1 & 346.7 \end{bmatrix}; \underline{B}_{hour} = [\underline{0}];$$

$$\underline{D}_{hour}^{(s=1)} = \begin{bmatrix} 16.6 & 0 \\ 0 & 43.2 \end{bmatrix}; \underline{D}_{hour}^{(s=0.5)} = \begin{bmatrix} 4.2 & 0 \\ 0 & 10.8 \end{bmatrix}; \underline{D}_{hour}^{(s=0.25)} = \begin{bmatrix} 1.0 & 0 \\ 0 & 2.7 \end{bmatrix}$$

212 For the hourglass shape the matrices form are the same of the first case: in
213 particular $\underline{D}_{hour}^{s=1} \approx 4 \underline{D}_{hour}^{s=0.5} \approx 16 \underline{D}_{hour}^{s=0.25}$. The negative terms $A_{1122} = A_{2211}$
214 show the auxetic behavior of the structure.

215 The constitutive matrix for the skew shape finally is:

$$\underline{A}_{skew} = \begin{bmatrix} 793.1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1104.7 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 934.8 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 566.5 \end{bmatrix};$$

$$\underline{B}_{skew}^{T(s=1)} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & -85.5 & 51.8 \\ 0 & 62.2 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}; \underline{B}_{skew}^{T(s=0.5)} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & -42.8 & 25.9 \\ 0 & 31.1 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix};$$

$$\underline{B}_{skew}^{T(s=0.25)} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & -21.4 & 13.0 \\ 0 & 15.6 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\underline{D}_{skew}^{(s=1)} = \begin{bmatrix} 26.6 & 0 \\ 0 & 31.3 \end{bmatrix}; \underline{D}_{skew}^{(s=0.5)} = \begin{bmatrix} 6.6 & 0 \\ 0 & 7.8 \end{bmatrix}; \underline{D}_{skew}^{(s=0.25)} = \begin{bmatrix} 1.7 & 0 \\ 0 & 2.0 \end{bmatrix}$$

216 For the skew shape the terms B_{222} , B_{121} and B_{211} are non null and, as in the
 217 skew 7-blocks case, a coupling between stresses/curvatures (microcouples/strains)
 218 is present. One again approximately: $\underline{B}_{skew}^{s=1} \approx 2\underline{B}_{skew}^{s=0.5} \approx 4\underline{B}_{skew}^{s=0.25}$, $\underline{D}_{skew}^{s=1} \approx$
 219 $4\underline{D}_{skew}^{s=0.5} \approx 16\underline{D}_{skew}^{s=0.25}$.

220 Starting from the above constitutive matrices, using the same identification
 221 procedure the matrices for the classical Cauchy 2D problem have been calculated
 222 as follows [49]:

$$C = \begin{bmatrix} A_{1111} & A_{1122} & 0 \\ A_{2211} & A_{2222} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{2}[A_{1212} + A_{2121}] + A_{1221} \end{bmatrix}$$

223 It is useful to note that the Cauchy constitutive matrix does not change with the
 224 scale variation, differently from the Cosserat matrix.

225 The question of the RVE definition is still open and the answer can depend
 226 on the type of microstructure and on the consideration that in an energy equiv-
 227 alent discrete-continuum transition the material symmetry class of the discrete
 228 assembly must be preserved [31]. Here a numerical criterion is adopted. In order
 229 to select the RVE for the homogenization procedure here adopted, the external
 230 load work of the static analysis case studied in Sec. 5 has been calculated for the
 231 discrete assembly and for the micropolar model of both 7-blocks and 4-blocks unit
 232 cells. The comparison refers to the static analysis of a rectangular panel where
 233 the microstructure factor scale is 0.5 and the results are reported in Table 1. The
 234 analyses relative to the the scale 1 and scale 0.25 are omitted because they give
 235 analogously consequences. Basing on these results, the 7-blocks unit cell of Sub-
 236 sec. 3.1.1 has been selected as the RVE for the numerical simulations performed;
 237 furthermore the Cauchy constitutive matrices are calculated from the matrices
 238 showed in Subsec. 3.1.1.

Scale 0.5 - External work					
Shape	Discrete	7 Blocks	Error[%]	4 Blocks	Error[%]
Regular	0.0796	0.0722	-9.35	0.113	41.7
Hourglass	0.0569	0.0484	-14.9	0.0756	33.0
Skew	0.0650	0.0556	-14.5	0.0860	32.3

Table 1: External work results for the static analyses (Sec. 5).

239 4 Numerical implementation

240 In the next subsections a numerical implementation of the micropolar theory is
241 resumed and the discrete models adopted for the simulations are described.

242 4.1 Continuum model

243 The present finite element framework is based on the previous works [50] [57]. The
244 finite element enforces an approximation through nodal kinematic parameters as:

$$\underline{u} = \underline{\mathcal{N}} \underline{d}^e \quad (11)$$

245 The displacement vector for the present problem is given by:

$$\underline{d}^{eT} = [u_1^1 \dots u_1^4 \ u_2^1 \dots u_2^4 \ \omega^1 \dots \omega^4] \quad (12)$$

246 the finite element has 12 degrees of freedom. The matrix of the shape functions
247 takes the form [51] [57] :

$$\underline{\mathcal{N}} = \begin{bmatrix} \underline{N} & \underline{0} & \underline{0} \\ \underline{0} & \underline{N} & \underline{0} \\ \underline{0} & \underline{0} & \underline{N} \end{bmatrix} \quad (13)$$

248 where \underline{N} is the vector of the linear Lagrangian shape functions. The internal work
249 becomes [54]:

$$\delta U = \delta \underline{d}^{eT} h \int_A (\underline{D}\underline{\mathcal{N}})^T \underline{C} (\underline{D}\underline{\mathcal{N}}) dA \underline{d}^e = \delta \underline{d}^{eT} h \int_A \underline{B}^T \underline{C} \underline{B} dA \underline{d}^e \quad (14)$$

250 where $\underline{B} = \underline{D}\underline{\mathcal{N}}$, thus the element stiffness matrix is:

$$\underline{K}^e = \int_A \underline{B}^T \underline{C} \underline{B} dA \quad (15)$$

251 The potential of loads becomes:

$$\delta V = -\delta \underline{d}^{eT} h \int_A \underline{N}^T \underline{f} dV - \delta \underline{d}^{eT} \int_S \underline{N}^T \underline{p} dS = -\delta \underline{d}^{eT} (\underline{F}^e + \underline{P}^e) \quad (16)$$

252 where \underline{F}^e and \underline{P}^e are volume and surface force vectors respectively. Linear shape
253 functions are considered for the present implementation with reduced integration
254 for the micro-rotation ω [55]. To perform reduced integration the strain vector has
255 to be reordered by separating strain terms which are fully integrated and the ones
256 for which reduced integration is applied.

257 Once the problem is solved in terms of displacements other quantities such as
258 stresses and relative rotation have to be post computed [55].

259 4.2 Discrete model

260 The discrete solution has been obtained using the FEM software ABAQUS; be-
261 cause of the complexity to build the model through the program interface, Python
262 script codes have been prepared. Static analyses with three different discrete mod-
263 els are presented as a benchmark for the numerical study in order to show the
264 goodness of the adopted homogenization technique [31].

265 4.2.1 Spring model

266 In the first model three linear elastic springs, longitudinal, transversal and rota-
 267 tional, are assigned at the center of each joints. For the edges parallel to axis x
 268 or y , springs are represented in the joint local reference system The scripts are
 269 structured in the following principal steps:

- 270 1. the geometry of the hexagonal shape is defined;
- 271 2. the material properties are defined;
- 272 3. the parts of the model are created;
- 273 4. the boundary blocks of the panel are cut to define the rectangular geometry
 274 panel;
- 275 5. edges are partitioned to define the middle point for each joint;
- 276 6. rotational and translational springs are added for all internal joints.

277 The single block must behave as a rigid body, therefore the material is assigned
 278 as an elastic isotropic behavior with a high value of the Young modulus with
 279 respect to the joint stiffness in particular $E = 100$ MPa. The normal stiffness is
 280 represented by the k_{11} term in reference to the normal direction to the contact
 281 area and the tangential stiffness by the term k_{22} along the contact area plane in
 282 the local system.

Fig. 5: Example of a single tile for the hourglass shape with elastic springs and local reference systems.

283 Energetic equivalence is used to carry out the rotational stiffness [54]:

$$k_r = k_{11} \frac{d}{2} \quad (17)$$

284 where d is the generic edge length of the single tile. Finally the boundary condi-
 285 tions, loads and the mesh of model are manually input.

286 4.2.2 Contact interaction

287 The elements, the joints and the texture of the discrete model are realized through
 288 Python script. However, in the present implementation the interactions between

289 rigid blocks is considered as distributed contact with the ABAQUS interaction
 290 option "surface interaction". The pressure-overclosure relationship are prescribed
 291 by using a linear elastic law: the surfaces transmit contact pressure when the
 292 overclosure between them, measured in the contact (normal) direction, is greater
 293 than zero. The linear pressure-overclosure relationship is identical to a tabular
 294 relationship with two data points, where the first point is located at the origin,
 295 it is necessary to specify the slope of the pressure-overclosure relationship, k . For
 296 the the tangential direction it is set the friction formulation as "frictionless" to
 297 consider the case with no tangential stiffness, in this way ABAQUS assumes that
 298 surfaces in contact slide freely without friction. It is considered this particular
 299 case for the difficulty to define a linear elastic tangential behavior as done for the
 300 normal direction. Various numerical tests have been done and the results are very
 301 close to the springs model, obviously with only a normal and rotational springs;
 302 the quality of the test indicates the right calculation for the rotational stiffness.

303 4.2.3 Elastic Interfaces

304 The third approach considers linear elastic interfaces among the blocks. Two parts
 305 in ABAQUS are created: one for the rigid blocks and one for the elastic interfaces.
 306 The mechanical properties of the materials were defined for the rigid block as
 307 orthotropic behavior with a high Young modulus and for the elastic interfaces
 308 engineering constants are set in order to fictitiously model a frictionless elastic
 309 interface with $G_{13} = G_{23} = G_{12} = 0$. The Young modulus was calculated as
 310 $EA/l = k_n s/l$, therefore $E = k_n s/A$ where: E is the Young modulus, A is the
 311 interface contact area, $A = td$; with d the edge length (because in this case the
 312 contact is developed along the whole surfaces) and t is the panel thickness. k_n
 313 is the normal spring stiffness and s thickness of the layer. Thus, assuming a unitary
 314 thickness $t = 1$, the modulus becomes:

$$E = \frac{k_n s}{d} \quad (18)$$

315 The Young modulus E increases with the decrease of the scale. Subsequently from
 316 the blocks and interfaces parts two instances were created: then they were bonded
 317 by the "tie constraints", that give them the same displacements at the contact
 318 interface. For explanatory purposes, using the three discrete systems previously
 319 described, in Fig. 6 a comparison of the vertical displacements for a panel clamped
 320 at the bottom with a vertical concentrated force at the center of the upper edge
 321 is reported.

Fig. 6: Vertical displacement component for discrete models with regular hexagonal shape scale $s = 1$ and vertical load applied at the top. a) Elastic springs b) Elastic contact c) Elastic interface.

322 From the vertical displacement contour plot a greater similarity between the
 323 spring and contact models can be detected, in particular for the panel region far
 324 from the applied load. The discrete model with elastic springs has been used for a
 325 comparison with the equivalent micropolar continuum model: this case is closer to
 326 the theoretical discrete model presented in [12] [49] and [58]. Moreover, the springs
 327 model is faster with respect to the model with contact interactions for which the
 328 computational cost increases exponentially with the scale reduction. In addition,
 329 contact interfaces leads to a non linear model on the contrary springs interfaces
 330 are linear.

331 5 Simulations

332 In this section, the behavior of 2D rectangular panels with different microstructural
 333 shape and different scales is investigated in Fig. 7, the panel is clamped at the base
 334 and a vertical load is applied at the top side center, for a footprint length equals
 335 $a = L_x/4$, L_x being the base length. The resultant of the load is a force of intensity
 336 $P = 10$ N, the stiffness terms are $k_{11} = 785$ N/m and $k_{22} = 392.5$ N/m and the
 337 length of panel sides are $L_x = 6.6$ m, $L_y = 7.7$ m for the regular hexagonal shape,
 338 $L_x = 5$ m, $L_y = 7.7$ m for the hourglass shape and $L_x = 5.85$ m, $L_y = 7.7$ m for
 339 the skew shape.

Fig. 7: Rectangular panel, static scheme.

340 In the next sections, a displacement field comparison among the discrete spring
341 model and the micropolar and classical continuum models is reported.

342 5.1 Regular hexagonal shape

Fig. 8: Horizontal displacement component, regular hexagonal shape.

343 Horizontal components of displacement are shown: the contour plot of the mi-
344 cropolar continuum is in line with the discrete system. There are not evident
345 differences among the Cosserat and Cauchy model. This is expected because of
346 the orthotetragonal configuration of regular hexagons, that implies corresponding
347 results among all the models [11].

Fig. 9: Vertical displacement component, regular hexagonal shape.

348 For vertical displacements the micropolar continuum contour plot is in line with
 349 the discrete system behavior, once again because of the orthotetragonal configu-

350 ration no evident differences among the Cosserat and Cauchy model are revealed
351 and their differences vanish when the microstructure scale factor become smaller.

352 5.2 Hourglass shape

Fig. 10: Horizontal displacement component, hourglass shape.

353 Horizontal displacements are shown: the contour plot of the micropolar continua
354 is in line with the discrete system. At the top of the panel a smaller maximum
355 displacement increase can be noted with the scale reduction for the discrete system.

Fig. 11: Vertical displacement component, hourglass shape.

356 Also for the vertical displacements the micropolar continuum contour plot is in
357 line with the discrete system behavior. The effect of negative Poisson ratio is visible
358 in this configuration which displays concentrated vertical displacements which are
359 close to zero far from the applied load, this is due to the horizontal contraction of
360 the material. A major displacement distribution can be noted for the micropolar
361 model respect to the classical model: moreover, for the hourglass shape a major
362 percolation [59] is visible for the Cosserat model respect to the Cauchy continuum
363 and this behavior is closer to the discrete system plot.

364 5.3 Skew shape

Fig. 12: Horizontal displacement component, skew shape.

365 The micropolar continuum model reproduces accurately the discrete system be-
366 havior, once again for the horizontal displacements there are not obvious differ-
367 ences among the three continuum models. For the discrete system, with the scale
368 reduction a smaller displacement magnitude increase can be noted at the panel
369 top.

Fig. 13: Vertical displacement component, skew shape.

370 Also for the vertical displacements field the micropolar continuum gives a faith-
 371 ful representation for the discrete system contour plot and once again the Cosserat
 372 model reveal a major distribution of the level curves in comparison with the Cauchy

373 model. Lastly as already shown for the hourglass shape, in the skew shape contour
374 plot the percolation effect is more evident for the micropolar model.

375 **6 Conclusion**

376 The present work investigates the static behavior of composite materials with
377 three types of hexagonal microstructures as equivalent micropolar media. The
378 comparison among the discrete model and the continuum models highlighted that
379 assemblies of regular hexagons have an orthotetragonal behavior, therefore there
380 is only a weak dependence on the scale, as in the case of materials with elements
381 of small size, and it has been shown that their homogenized behavior is close to
382 the behavior of classical elastic bodies. For the hourglass and skew configuration,
383 the scale dependence is more evident both for the discrete system and for the
384 micropolar continuum, which properly accounts for the non-symmetries as well as
385 size effects exhibited by the discrete system, as consequence, this last should be
386 preferred in this cases. It is then highlighted the scale dependence of the discrete
387 system and how the Cosserat model takes into account it, differently for the Cauchy
388 model, and how to consider the asymmetric behavior of anisotropic materials is
389 fundamental.

390 Moreover, the static analyses comparison shows that the homogenization tech-
391 nique can be generalized for hexagonal geometry microstructure, both for concave
392 shapes and convex shapes [12] [31] [33] [32] [58]. For the study of particle com-
393 posites the possibility to use a proven homogenization technique involves in a
394 faster and efficient computational modeling. Furthermore three discrete models
395 have been used to study composite materials described as materials made of rigid
396 particles and elastic interfaces. The comparison between them show the right as-
397 sumption to calculate the interface rotational stiffness. The elastic spring model
398 is a linear model more faster for the numerical simulation compared to other two
399 and it well represent the mathematical theoretical model adopted for the discrete
400 system representation. Finally, other geometries can be investigated in the future
401 comparing the discrete system and the continuum model and as well as the dy-
402 namic case can be studied.

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